

ANTIMICROBIAL PEPTIDES FROM DOMESTIC & FARM ANIMALS AND ITS USES IN VETERINARY MEDICINE

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ABSTRACT

Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) are naturally occurring substances vital to the innate immune response against various pathogens. Over 4000 AMPs have been identified, with around 3000 sequences cataloged in databases, predominantly derived from animals and plants. They exhibit broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity, classified based on their source, composition, and activity, including antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, antiparasitic, and antitumor properties. AMPs can be synthesized either constitutively or in response to pathogens, interacting with microbial membranes to compromise their integrity and induce lysis. Their application in veterinary medicine extends to immunomodulation, dietary supplementation, gut microbiota modulation, and combating multidrug-resistant infections. While AMPs show promise as alternatives to traditional antibiotics, resistance mechanisms have been observed. Continued research is essential for understanding their full potential and ensuring safety and efficacy in veterinary applications, thereby benefiting both animal and human health without promoting new microbial resistance.

KEYWORDS: Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs), Cathelicidins, Defensins, Lingual antimicrobial peptide, Equine Lysozyme (EL), Prophenins, Protegrins.

INTRODUCTION

In conjunction with increasing efforts at antibiotic stewardship, bacterial resistance to currently available antibiotics has prompted research into alternate infection management strategies. Naturally occurring substances called antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) are generated by all bacterial and eukaryotic cells and may one day replace traditional antibiotics. Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) are the tiny molecular peptides that play a critical role in the innate immunity of the host against a broad range of pathogens, including bacteria, fungi, parasites and viruses. Numerous biological processes including immunological control, angiogenesis, wound healing, and anticancer activity, have been discovered to be possessed by AMPs.

More than 4000 natural antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) have been found to date, and roughly 3000 sequences from animal and plant species

have been recorded in various databases. These molecules are peptides with 12–50 amino acids; they are typically positively charged because arginine and lysine residues make up about 50% of their amino acids; they are referred to as antimicrobials because of their broad-spectrum activity against a variety of microorganisms, including parasites, fungi, viruses, and Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria.

CLASSIFICATION OF AMPS & EXAMPLES

Based on source

- Mammalian source: Cathelicidins, Defensins
- Amphibians derived: Cancrin, Magainin
- Insect derived: Jellein, Cercopins
- Microbial source: Nisin, Gramicidin

Based on composition

- Proline rich: pPR-AMP1, Tur1A
- Glycine rich: Attacins, Diptericins
- Histidine rich: L4H4, HV2